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CERVICAL EROSION**Omanova Risolat Ilhom qizi**

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Abstract: Uterine erosion - of the mucous membrane of the cervix damage Violation of the normal state of the mucous membrane can be caused by physical and chemical factors. In some cases, the uterus in childless women the cause of erosion of the neck may be an anomaly in the development of the epithelium. Taking into account the nature of the origin, the disease is a real erosion and pseudo-erosion (ectopia) is divided into types.

Key words: endocervicosis, cervical ectopy, pseudoerosion, congenital erosion, true erosion

Cervical erosion (endocervicosis, ectopy of the cervix) is a violation of the integrity of the mucous membrane of the vaginal part, a defect or covering with wounds. Erosion opens the way for infection to enter the uterus and its appendages and causes the development of chronic inflammatory diseases of the small pelvis, and can even lead to infertility.

At the gynecologist's appointment, almost every second patient is diagnosed with cervical erosion. In general, this disease is one of the most common pathologies in women of childbearing age. The most dangerous complication of uterine erosion is the possibility of its transformation into a low-quality tumor. Therefore, it is very important to detect this disease as soon as possible.

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Causes of cervical erosion

- early onset of sexual activity, frequent change of sexual partners
- Sexual infections and inflammatory diseases of the female genital organs
- Traumatic effects
- Hormonal and immunological disorders

Physiological or "congenital" erosion of the cervix, which occurs in young women under the age of 25, tends to self-heal

Signs of cervical erosion

In most cases, erosion of the cervix rarely manifests itself clinically, and often such a diagnosis is found during a gynecological examination.

But the patients themselves turn to the gynecologist with a complaint about spots not related to menstruation, especially after sex. Women may experience symptoms such as pain and purulent discharge during intercourse. The latter is associated with the addition of inflammatory diseases to erosion, which significantly worsens the course of the disease.

Diagnosis of cervical diseases

At the first visit, after a visual examination, the gynecologist can diagnose cervical erosion. However, a visual inspection is not always enough to make sure that your judgments are correct and to make a decision on treatment tactics, a number of diagnostic measures should be carried out:

- examination in mirrors in a gynecological chair;
- screening for sexually transmitted infections
- cytological examination of cervical material - oncocytology
- Colposcopy - involves examination of the cervix using an optical device that allows the image to be magnified several times.
- Cervical biopsy - a small piece of cervical tissue is taken, its detailed study allows establishing the final diagnosis.

Such a complex of diagnostic manipulations allows the doctor to make an accurate diagnosis and develop the necessary tactics for treating the patient.

Treatment of cervical erosion

- Anti-inflammatory drugs, hormonal drugs, if necessary, antibacterial and antiviral drugs, local drugs are prescribed. The complex of therapeutic measures also includes drugs aimed at increasing immunity and restorative properties.

- Chemical coagulation - the cervix is treated with special preparations that have a caustic effect, as a result of which scabs appear.
- Cryodestruction - the erosion area is treated with liquid nitrogen, the damaged area is "frozen" into healthy tissue using a thin and very cold manipulator.
- Laser coagulation - the area of erosion is exposed to a targeted surgical laser beam.
- Radio wave surgery is the latest breakthrough in the field of surgical treatment of erosion. Treatment of erosion is carried out without pressure on the tissues, reducing tissue damage. In addition, electric burns are completely excluded, the technique of radiosurgery is not traumatic.

Types of uterine erosion:

Pseudoerosion

Refers to a round red area with a diameter of 5 mm. Pus may form on it, especially if the disease has been going on for a long time. Pseudoerosion is typical for girls with a high level of female hormones in their blood, and the pathology may extend beyond the border of the cervical canal. Pseudoerosion is dangerous because it can turn into a tumor of poor quality.

Congenital erosion

Sometimes, during the examination of young or teenage girls, the gynecologist determines the displacement of the cylindrical epithelium on the cervix, and during colposcopy, it can be seen that it is painted in a bright red color. This is called congenital erosion and there is no need to treat it, because in practice it never turns into an oncological disease.

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